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CHANGING MACROECONOMICS DUE TO THE "TRUST" COMPONENT

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Abstract

In the article, the authors present a discussion that arose at the end of the first decade of the twentieth century. In economics regarding the fact that modern neoclassical macroeconomics not only failed to predict the crisis (2007–2010), warn of its occurrence, and offer some damping procedures, but even after the crisis occurred, failed to give intelligible explanations and recipes for overcoming it. The authors consider the discussion developed by P. Krugman and D. Stiglitz, as well as D. Akerlof and R. Schiller in a series of their publications. The authors singled out a posteriori "alternative" economists like D. Akerlof and R. Schiller who built new macroeconomics, the models of which, in their opinion, should consider trust, the effect of panic or herd behavior of market agents, etc. The authors also highlighted the main idea that the epidemics of optimism or pessimism in modern markets, arising from the change in trust and the spread of ideas that take possession of agents, reproduce the mechanism of the crisis.

Keywords: Microeconomic level of analysis, behavioral macroeconomics, structural parameters of the economic system, time intervals.

A rather frank criticism of the "money illusion", the significance of inflationary expectations in decision-making by economic agents during the crisis of 2007-2010, boiled down to the fact that the assumption of neoclassical economists that people adjust for inflation in their actions is unreliable. As an illustrative example, the case of concluding labor contracts is used when the agent does not include wage indexation in the contract under the inflation rate. Thus, the agent acts according to the unspoken rule of "money illusion," focusing on nominal values and estimates, forgetting that only real indicators are important. Here, it should tie wages to changes in real purchasing power.

The problem is that the agent cannot include indexation in the employment contract, and the employer does not want to do this for a known reason. As a result, wages lag inflation, but this does not mean at all that as inflationary processes develop in the economy, agents do not expand their demands for wage increases. If wages were automatically indexed, and institutions encouraged such indexation, then inflation would certainly be higher, providing a certain lag in the dynamics of prices and wages, anyway.

Wages as labor costs are part of the price of any product or service. Therefore, there is a correlation between the dynamics of prices and wages. Another thing is what this relationship is in short and long time intervals. It seems important to clarify that a macroeconomic theory based on such a relationship will never be

correct since it does not consider other factors of inflation and the motives for obtaining wages. The fact is that agents, when agreeing to work under a contract, often proceed from ideas about the standard of living, and not from an assumption of what inflation will be. Roughly estimating their wages, they agree to a certain standard of consumption and life, such an assessment implicitly, but consider inflationary changes. Let's say a subway driver won't agree to a salary below 1,500 GEL because the work intensity is high, the costs of restoring lost health are high, and the standard of living in Tbilisi requires high costs for medical services and food. It is interesting to note that the employer may proceed from the same criterion, realizing the shortage of such a profession, and will not assign wages below the specified amount. In order to attract agents and create the demand for a driver's position in the Tbilisi metro, the employer may overestimate the specified amount in order to have a selection of specialists and ultimately set wages under the perception of the standard of living in Tbilisi.

When talking with a taxi driver, we asked why he works for a price, providing himself with a profitability of 55% for transporting a passenger 10 km (we calculated the cost of gasoline in advance, added the driver's time, the risk of wear and tear on the car, which is negligible at such a distance, and so on). We were wondering why the shipping price is not calculated correctly even if there is a meter. The answer was very simple

(the driver admitted all drivers know the elementary calculation rules, but no one is going to apply them), that he proceeds from the total amount that he must bring to the family. Based on this benchmark, and not the actual cost of individual service, the price of passenger transportation for a certain distance is formed. Summing up such actions of agents in the macroeconomic system, we get an important determinant of inflation, which is reduced to the standard of consumption and inflation itself in the previous period. These processes are institutionalized and determine future inflation, laying it in the motives and actions of economic agents.

Thus, inflation expectations are taken into account one way or another by agents, only it is camouflaged, not so obvious, and, of course, can be inaccurate, erroneous, for example, overestimated or underestimated. The more unexpectedly prices change, the higher the speed of such or institutional changes and the more frankly agents will consider inflation in labor contracts and other actions.

Recommendations for exiting the analysis, as seen by pro-Keynesian economists, should be reduced to the organization of monetary and budgetary policy, which would presumably be full employment of the population, with a deviation from the "control" parameter, restoring emissions to the value of the value. If there is a crisis in the country that occurs in the financial system, the level of confidence is. How can a solution be found? Apparently, it remains either to increase spending, to accept taxes, or to do both. However, the probability of non-reduction of budget revenues remains tiny. They can argue that the poisoning occurred at the same time rather hard. Suspicious spending alerts and alerts. D. Akerlof and R. Schiller advocate the idea of "strong lending", such an increase in loans that it would have the effect of ensuring full employment. They are comparable to the Kahn-Kanes multiplier, mimicking the confidence multiplier. The so-called macroeconomic irrational economics that they wish to plan, built on diseases other than neoclassical ones, involves an active evaluation of the concepts of "trust" and "irrational beginning". Behind this is a serious task - to create a financial mathematics that calculates macroeconomic finance, considering the irrationality and institutional constraints in the coming years of agents. [1; 25]

The multiplier theory explains economic growth and depression. Multipliers for investments, expenditures, government spending, etc. were introduced. These performance indicators are like income when using their content. The same goes for trust. Growth or an unhealthy level of confidence in some small amount can lead to an increase in income. This logic is correct. But, first, it involves the measurement of reliability by precise methods and the scale of confidence in the macroeconomic sense. Such a problem is very difficult at the economic macroeconomic level and even for large markets. Secondly, if there is, as is claimed, a trust multiplier, there must also exist a multiplier of irrationality or naturalness as two models of agents' behavior. In addition, the level of optimism or pessimism probably depends on the health of the agents. Therefore, it is possible to introduce the function of the agent's health stock

and talk about the multiplier of this function, which will be plausible, the occurrence of human disease is still inclined to a lower level of trust, and, perhaps, the incidence, shows its position, trusts, on the contrary, it happens to the way of salvation, as long. To what extent will it be necessary to "operationalize" macroeconomics? This is an important question in method and discovery, and we have been able to cover it in the disclosing reasoning.

The current level of confidence may indeed be a certain future consumption volume with some time lag. And what does the level of trust depend on? Perhaps, as the country's population ages or ages, will this level rise or fall? Optimism and a greater level of trust, and old age, characterize youth with high loads, of course, a lower level of trust. Therefore, aging nations are less trusting than younger ones. However, this thesis is still not implemented empirically, if you follow sociological surveys and create trust indices that are calculated by calculated methods. In particular, this is how the index of consumer preferences is considered, which is recognized as a conditional right assumption and can be changed as a certain trust index.

Note that the neoclassical macroeconomics at the forefront must change the dependence on the natural rate. Macroeconomists, who include the problems of trust in the analysis and the identified solutions when choosing solutions, albeit with some reservations, link their reasoning precisely to this theory. It is argued that the natural level has become the basis of macroeconomic policy, and it is this theory that suggests the absence of the "money illusion" that makes up the whole thought of macroeconomic science. But critics of neoclassical macroeconomics, in particular D. Akerlof and R. Schiller, do not depart from this idea either. Of course, the subordination of macroeconomic instruments to the full institution of employment, when the connection of labor markets and regulating these markets is weak, looks inadequate, even if it includes trust and the multiplier trusts in this analysis.

Measures such as capturing the discount window, direct investment in banks to saturate the economy with liquidity, and easing funding constraints have strong goals of revitalizing demand and are certainly not a requirement. The reasons for the questions about how much they are extremely necessary, and even more so, are sufficient. The deployment of the crisis becomes possible not for some objective reasons, but because of the organization of the work of financial and, more broadly, economic institutions, which, without changing interact with each other over time in such a way that they provoke a crisis.

The effectiveness of the government's macroeconomic measures will be determined by the stage of the crisis at which these measures will be applied, i.e., the dependence on the depth and dynamics of the crisis that has already begun will become obvious. This dependency will determine both the scale of measures applied and the number of instruments. The well-known "goals-instruments" principle of J. Tinbergen, which says that the number of economic policy instruments must be equal to the number of goals, otherwise the

goals will not be achieved, does not consider the institutional organization of economic policy. Economics and effects arise from the psychology of the behavior of agents and their irrational beginning. Having a smaller number of tools, it is possible to fully realize some parallel goals, which are not directly related to the tools, and if the goals and tools are equal, the goals cannot be achieved because of the consuming effect. transaction costs or X-inefficiency of the economic system or management system. Thus, the principle postulates an ideal (minimum) or even desirable ratio, which follows from the corresponding mathematical concepts. Its institutional expansion requires clarification of both the conditions for applying the principle and those institutional structures that can ensure their result in each specific case if the number of goals and instruments of economic policy does not match. Of course, these measures to stimulate aggregate demand can have a positive impact on employment and production. They may not be enough to overcome the crisis with the help of financial and economic institutions. If we carry out the logic of reasoning further, then we should note a medical analogy when the symptoms of the disease are removed, but the nature of this disease and the methods of its treatment have not been fully established. Are not selected. [2; 15]

It is interesting to note that the causes of the crisis, unlike the previous ones, are named adequately to what was observed, namely: not low demand or even high energy prices, although all this accompanied the crisis of 2007–2009, there were causes of the crisis, but a lack of credit, or rather a collapse of liquidity, a credit deficit. In fact, they're certainly combined these reasons, they can extend the list of which beyond these three factors. This allegedly implies the need to solve the problem of credit deficit in such a way as to achieve a situation of full employment at the macroeconomic level. This logic seems "linear" and self-evident. And such a measure extremely does not ensure a controlled exit from the crisis and prevent its recurrence. Of course, it is necessary to limit speculation in derivatives and other securities, as well as to regulate the process of securitization. This will require the instrumentalization of the management of the financial system and its change. The general overestimated and unjustified optimism generated by speculation, as well as the difference between issuing short-term and long-term loans (when money is taken for a short term, and issued to agents for a longer term) ensured the low efficiency of the main financial and banking institutions. As a result, the liquidity of the entire economic system collapsed. By simply cutting taxes, increasing budget expenditures (these two measures are opposite in implementation - it is difficult to simultaneously reduce taxes and increase spending), as well as lowering the interest rate, although these measures will not be useless, it is difficult to quickly solve the problem of changing the psychology of agents formed under the influence of existing institutions. It is necessary to deprive them of opportunities that essentially destroyed macroeconomic stability, giving rise to a crisis. This task at the level of institutional planning and design seems to be quite difficult since they needed

costs that could reorient agents. Economists do not consider such costs. Using the term "trust" here requires clarification, since even without trusting financial institutions, agents have the opportunity not to withdraw their funds if alternative opportunities are unattractive to them. [3;45]

Note that the crisis of 2007–2009 was not related to the fact that agents withdrew their capital (capital flight), as, for example, in Thailand in 1997, which caused a massive devaluation. In the present case, we did not observe anywhere a strong devaluation. There was a renewed crisis of global capitalism, a crisis of its financial institutions, eating up money resources and impoverishing the production sectors with credit. Let us emphasize that the planning of macroeconomic policy based on the natural rate hypothesis, which links credit with the need to ensure full employment, seems to be an inaccurate and outdated method of macroeconomic policy. As for the introduction of the confidence factor, this is not a new theory of macroeconomics, as D. Akerlof and R. Schiller believe. The reasons here are:

First, inflation cannot be determined by one factor and only with it is so tightly connected in the short or long run. This refers to the unemployment factor. The higher the unemployment, the lower the inflation. And when unemployment is low, inflation becomes quotation, and mutual determination, based on the Phillips curve, is quite difficult to confirm because the phenomenon of unemployment depends on the state of labor markets and structural changes in the economy (intersectoral dynamics). Such a ratio is a model, and they clearly showed the deviation from this model by the years of stagnation when both inflation and unemployment were high.

Second, besides the unemployed, who have a peculiar motivation and very severe restrictions on personal income and consumption levels, there are agents in the economy with a completely different behavior model - those who have a job but show different activity, i.e. innovators and conservatives (conservatives). - imitators). It is they, interacting, and experiencing various transitional states, that most of all determine the process of price dynamics, i.e. inflation. If this is not the case, then it turns out that the smallest group of agents in their total reaction is more strongly associated with inflation. However, the unemployed person does not influence the pricing process, and even the demand from this group of agents is very insignificant to ensure demand inflation. Then why do macroeconomists, starting from the natural rate hypothesis, attach so much importance to the relationship between unemployment and inflation? The fact is that the hypothesis of the natural level establishes the amount of employment in the economy, which is accepted as an acceptable and even necessary value.

The natural level hypothesis comes from the position that agents do not have the "money illusion", so they rationally decide about prices and inflation, as well as other events, for example, the psychological factors of changing the reactions of agents in macroeconomics were considered by John M. Keynes. [4, 9; 5, 32]

In fact, one point is established (and the need to strive for it) as the main direction of macroeconomic

policy. The structural characteristics of the economy, and the need to apply the instruments of macroeconomic policy to achieve the structural relationships with such a philosophy of macroeconomic policy are not taken into account. The equilibrium of the economy and its greatest efficiency will allegedly be achieved at the point of full employment, where a certain level of unemployment remains, but it does not contribute to either inflation or deflation, i.e., it is neutral to price dynamics (inflation-neutral level). It is believed that in the economy of markets, there is always unemployment as a certain indicator of the flexibility of the system, its development is not on the production possibilities curve, but somewhat lower, which makes it possible to maneuver and increase results in all directions, and not because of transferring resources from one direction of development to another. The value of the natural level for each country is different and over time can also change, for example, increase. This means agreeing or recognizing a relative increase in the number of unemployed in the economy as the norm. Economic policy becomes tied to this natural level and seeks to bring the system to the natural level point as the position of greatest efficiency, as is commonly believed according to the theories of M. Friedman and other representatives of the Chicago School of Economics. [6, 27]

Note that if we proceed from the natural level hypothesis, then we will not be able to say anything about other factors of unemployment and inflation, about the length of stay at the natural level point, about the flexibility of macroeconomic policy instruments and their the ability to bring the situation to this equilibrium state. Estimating the scale of such a phenomenon as unemployment depends strongly on the definition of this phenomenon and the method of accounting. More precisely, the rules by which unemployment is recorded. The level of social protection and the amount of government social programs that influence decisions regarding job changes and becoming unemployed may motivate agents who act according to these rules and in their actions. The natural level hypothesis does not see the institutional effects of the functioning of the economic system at all.

When the level of trust of agents is low, it is rather difficult to expect a massive spread of innovations in the economy. The same agent can be an innovator, a conservative, and an imitator, depending on the institutional conditions, the monetary support of its activities, and government measures. There is a permanent switching of the strategy depending on certain conditions. Trust is built through painstaking effort and is associated with consistent, factual actions that bring satisfaction and are associated with the expected result. If one thing is expected and another is done, trust is quickly lost, as it disappears with massive opportunism. It can dampen the risk of loss of income because of competition, so the trust factor is quite important in shaping the economic motivation of agents. [7; 20]

The presence of innovators, conservatives, and imitators in the economy, and their activity in certain periods, can influence price dynamics. This influence can be such that, in particular, the growth in the number

of innovators and innovations will be accompanied by upward price dynamics and an increase in unemployment, and the measures taken by the government, based on the logic of the “natural level hypothesis”, in this case, will lead to the curtailment of this trend. The dominance of conservatives and imitators may keep the rate of price growth at a stable level, but a reduction in the group of innovators will cause an increase in unemployment. As we can see, the ratio between the contribution of various groups of agents to inflation and economic development actually determines and explains the deviation from the Philipps curve model, when there can be high inflation, high unemployment, and relatively non-increasing inflation with rising unemployment. The analysis should be clearly multifactorial and consider many aspects of the named macroeconomic phenomena. It will be plausible only in this case.

Third, employers, which are a special type of economic agent pursuing a wage and employment policy at the micro-level, have learned to calculate labor costs in such a way as to reduce actual wages while maintaining the rate of profit, which is important for them and the owners. To do this, an employee is assigned a fixed salary, salary, a whole system of allowances and bonuses is introduced, which seems to be tied to the results of labor, often to profit. When a crisis unfolds in the economy or a crisis period arises for a particular company, the employer simply removes these allowances, which are not regulated by labor legislation, since each company has its own. As a result, the employee's actually paid wages are reduced, and it is almost impossible or very difficult to protest such actions (transaction costs are high). Thus, the ratchet effect exists, i.e., prices for various factors of production are frigid to decrease, i.e., resistant to decrease, and there are clear opportunities for reducing wages (labor prices) for the “labor” factor. This is the factor in the reduction of savings during periods of crisis, and they also reduced savings because of financial destabilization, devaluation, and a reduction in the banking's liquidity system. An employee entering into an employment contract that involves a fixed salary and a system of allowances must understand that the contract not only does not include expected inflation but *de facto* and *de jure* requires agreement to the possibility of deflation of the employee's labor cost. We should note that a new behavioral macroeconomic theory cannot emerge from incorporating certain psychological effects and updated parameters, such as the confidence multiplier, into old analytical constructs. A new theory can arise only through a fundamental study of the microeconomic foundations of macroeconomics with a clear picture of changing behavior patterns of groups of agents, and institutions, as well as economic policy instruments aimed at achieving stable non-equilibrium states and expected changes in the behavior of microeconomic agents of an irrational beginning. [8; 15]

“Behavioral” and “structural” macroeconomics. According to D. Akerlof and R. Schiller [1], the modern macroeconomic theory describes well the situation with rational reactions of agents under the action of economic motives of behavior (table).

Areas Where Modern Macroeconomics is Strong (+) and Weak (-)

Agent Reactions / Motives	Economic	Noneconomic
Irrational	–	–
Rational	+	–

However, regarding cases with irrational reactions of agents not with economic and non-economic motives of behavior (with rational and irrational reactions), but under the existing facts of life, classical macroeconomics does not give convincing answers. Therefore, it is logical that there is a need to consider behavioral aspects in macroeconomic models. In particular, we believe that trust can be one of those aspects that must not only be taken into account but also build models based on this factor. The assessment of trust can be carried out and is already being carried out using indices. We assume that trust has a strong influence on agents' expectations. Optimistic and pessimistic reactions (expectations) of agents affect aggregate demand, the change of which affects not wages, but employment, demand decreases unemployment increases. The irrational start of agents, the factor of trust, determines the shift in the demand curve.[9, 33; 10, 62]

With the significance of the “trust” factor, we should note that many other significant factors—technological, structural, changes in preferences and competitive substitution, etc. can influence a shift in the demand curve. Therefore, when the concept of “confidence multiplier” is introduced, which shows how much income changes when the level of confidence changes by one point, then we can also talk about other multipliers. For example, about the multiplier of the health function [3], on which the reactions of agents and their contribution to GDP depend, about the technological multiplier, or about the multiplier of the volume of knowledge. All these parameters, either, can influence the development of the economy and are quite significant in the present historical period, so it is impossible to neglect them.

It is interesting to note that the problem of trust arises initially in financial markets, which are dynamically developing and determine the macroeconomic dynamics. However, in economic transactions in traditional sectors of the economy, the problem of trust is also present, but it is more difficult to measure this trust since the indices applicable to assessing trust in financial markets are not suitable in this case. D. Akerlof and R. Schiller make an attempt, without deviating from classical macroeconomics, to add a behavioral aspect to it, deploying their technique based on the “natural level” hypothesis (although the authors call it a theory).

They permeated the economic system with hierarchies and structures. The rapid change of confidence in the financial markets as a macroeconomic factor is not capable of seriously changing the theory of macroeconomics, especially with a long-term orientation. Macroeconomic instruments should influence the economic

structure, incentives, motives, and reactions of the behavior of agents and, in this aspect, form a trust or influence it.

If a hierarchically superior agent chooses an agent of a lower one, then the rule comes into force according to which the cost of communication between them is cheaper than the cost of the decision itself. And the likelihood of harm due to failure to properly report to the agent is higher than the likelihood of equivalent damage. In the absence of a solution to the problem. In such a case, we will observe negative selection with a permanent fixation on the worst qualities of the hierarchy.

If the economic chains along which resources are distributed among the areas of activity n form a hierarchy and generate income y at each level, with the risk of losing funds, then the situation in the channels of the hierarchical system will be characterized by the ratio of net income to the cost of the resource (investment).

If we designate: resources - as ln , income at each level - as yn , risk of losing money - as r , amount of funds - as b , then it will be possible to calculate the ratio of net income to the cost of the resource (investment) using the formula:

$$di = yi - bi$$

Or:

$$di / Ij = yi (1 - rj) / Ij$$

In macroeconomics, a hierarchy can be distinguished according to the dominance of the industry in the creation of GDP. This indicator can characterize the industry and the risk in each of the industries will be different.

The impact on the distribution of resources/income and/or the risk profile of economic activity and the profitability of activities then becomes a central issue. This should form the basis of macroeconomic management and macroeconomic policy, and trust or distrust will be measured by indices not only in relation to financial markets but also in other sectors - purely separately, since in transactions it will, of course, be associated with risk.

A negative selection of solutions and tools in macroeconomics can arise because of the institutionalization (stabilization) of a negative quality (system dysfunction - see figure) [4]. A change in the trust of agents may not lead to any shifts in the demand curve, in principle. The sensitivity of demand to this factor is important. It is worth considering the sensitivity of supply to the same change in confidence, and not just demand, because the overall macroeconomic result will be determined by just such a cumulative change.

Figure 1. System dysfunction [4]

Behavior patterns of agents arise and change because of the motive of demonstrative behavior, the motive of envious comparison, the instinct of imitation, the law of social status, and other socio-psychological motives. The behavior of the wealthy class involves ostentatious consumption and the competitive aspect of consumption.

Conclusion

Thus, by appealing to the microeconomic level of analysis, T. Veblen lays the foundation of behavioral macroeconomics, where the main shifts are studied based on the initial position laid down.

It is important to note that macroeconomic theory should proceed from the need to assess the impact on the structural parameters of the economic system and ensure the proportions of economic development in the considered time intervals. This will ensure the growth of the product when achieving performance parameters, incentives for agents, development of institutional infrastructure, as well as an assessment of the total changes in the behavior of players and some of the most significant promising markets with rapid institutional changes.

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